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Thesis

For obtaining Agronomic Engineer's Diploma

Topic

Modelling the functional role of the microorganisms in the daily exchanges of carbon and nitrogen in cereals –legumes intercropping system: First validation of MOMOS model under Mediterranean conditions

Presented by: **KESKES Mohamed Islam**

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Abstract:

The modelling of the continuous exchange of carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) published previously in the literature is little focused on the functional role of micro-organisms. Concerning plant covers, this modeling was mostly performed in sole crop systems and poorly investigated under field conditions at the farm scale, in which evidence was lacking for intercropping. This work focus on the mechanistic modelling approaches based on the ecological functioning of microbial biomass (MB), in order to quantify the daily exchange of C and N between plant organs, micro-organisms, rhizobial symbionts, soil compartments and atmosphere. The MOMOS model was validated on C and N data collected from common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L. cv. El Djadida*)/ maize (*Zea mays L. cv. Filou*) intercropping system. Experiment was performed with two field sites chosen with farmers to represent two contrasted phosphorus (P)-soil conditions. Results show that all C and N exchanges were successfully predicted at 5% significance, they are often varied depending on the phenological stages, and so more during the flowering stage. The optimized C allocations from photosynthesis to root were contributed to increase both grain yield and N grain for intercropped maize. C and N stocks in common bean nodules were lower in intercropping than in sole crop. This was associated with the decrease of total N₂ fixation by intercropped common bean, in particular in high P-soil. However, the optimized rate of N fixation was greater in intercropping than in sole cropping system where P is limited in the soil. The most of C loss from soil was found mainly transferred by microorganisms to the atmosphere. It was significantly minimized in intercropped plots, in order to improve C use efficiency by living microorganism. These results uncover the strong link between N and C stocks, confirming the robustness of MOMOS equations that were newly formulated and checked in this thesis. The present agroecological modelling demonstrated the functional role of microbial biomass, in the growth of the mixed crop and symbiosis interaction, in order to predict better the daily C and N exchange flows between plant organs, soil compartments and atmosphere.

Keywords: Intercropping; Micro-organisms; plant symbionts; Mechanistic models; Continuous exchange

Résumé :

La modélisation de l'échange continu de carbone (C) et d'azote (N) publiée précédemment dans la littérature est peu focalisée sur le rôle fonctionnel des micro-organismes. En ce qui concerne les couvertures végétales, cette modélisation a été principalement réalisée dans des systèmes de culture unique et mal étudiée dans des conditions de terrain à l'échelle de l'exploitation, où les preuves faisaient défaut pour les cultures associées. Ces travaux portent sur les approches de modélisation mécaniste basées sur le fonctionnement écologique de la biomasse microbienne (MB), afin de quantifier les échanges quotidiens de C et N entre les organes végétaux, les micro-organismes, les symbiotes rhizobiens, les compartiments du sol et l'atmosphère. Le modèle MOMOS a été validé sur les données C et N collectées à partir d'un système de culture associée d'haricot commun (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L. cv. El Djadida) / maïs (*Zea mays* L. cv. Filou). L'expérience a été réalisée avec deux sites de terrain choisis avec des agriculteurs pour représenter deux conditions contrastées du sol au phosphore (P). Les résultats montrent que tous les échanges de C et N ont été prédits avec succès à une signification de 5%, ils sont souvent variés en fonction des stades phénologiques, et particulièrement pendant la phase de floraison. Les allocations optimisées de C de la photosynthèse à la racine ont contribué à augmenter à la fois le rendement en grains et en N pour le maïs en association. Les stocks de C et N dans les nodules de haricots communs étaient plus faibles en culture mixte qu'en culture unique. Ceci était associé à la diminution de la fixation totale de N₂ par le haricot commun qui se trouve en association avec maïs, en particulier dans les sols riches en P. Cependant, le taux optimisé de fixation de N était plus élevé en culture associée qu'en culture unique où le P est limité dans le sol. La majeure partie de la perte de C du sol a été principalement transférée par les micro-organismes dans l'atmosphère. Elle a été considérablement minimisée dans les parcelles de culture associée, afin d'améliorer l'efficacité d'utilisation du C par des microorganismes vivants. Ces résultats révèlent le lien étroit entre les stocks de N et de C, confirmant la robustesse des équations MOMOS nouvellement formulées et vérifiées dans cette thèse. La modélisation agroécologique actuelle a démontré le rôle fonctionnel de la biomasse microbienne, dans la croissance des cultures mixtes et les interactions symbiotiques, afin de mieux prédire les flux quotidiens d'échange de C et N entre les organes végétaux, les compartiments du sol et l'atmosphère.

Mots clés: culture associée ; Micro-organismes ; Modèles mécanistes ; Échange continu.

المخلص :

إن نمذجة التبادل المستمر للكربون (C) والنيتروجين (N) المنشورة سابقاً تركز قليلاً على الدور الوظيفي للكائنات الحية الدقيقة. فيما يتعلق بأغذية النباتات ، تم إجراء هذه النمذجة في الغالب في أنظمة المحاصيل الفردية وتم التحقيق فيها بشكل سيئ في ظل الظروف الميدانية على نطاق المزرعة ، حيث لم يكن هناك دراسات على الزراعة البيئية. يركز هذا العمل على مناهج النمذجة الميكانيكية القائمة على الأداء البيئي للكتلة الحيوية الميكروبية (MB) ، من أجل تحديد التبادل اليومي لـ C و N بين أعضاء النبات ، والكائنات الدقيقة ، والمتعايشات الجذرية ، ومكونات التربة والجو. تم التحقق من صحة النموذج MOMOS على بيانات C و N التي تم جمعها من نظام الزراعة البيئية للفاصوليا (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.* cv. *El الجديدة*) / الذرة (*Zea mays L. cv. Filou*). وتم إجراء التجربة مع موقعين حقلين ، حيث تم اختيارهما مع المزارعين لتمثيل حالتين متباينتين من الفسفور (P). أظهرت النتائج أن جميع التبادلات C و N تم التنبؤ بها بنجاح عند أهمية 5 % ، وغالباً ما تتنوع اعتماداً على المراحل الفينولوجية ، وهكذا أكثر خلال مرحلة الإزهار. ساهمت معاملات نقل الـ C المثلى من التمثيل الضوئي إلى الجذور في زيادة كل من محصول الحبوب و N الموجود في حبة الذرة خاصة في الزراعة البيئية. كان مخزون C و N في عقيدات الفاصوليا العادية أقل في زراعة المشتركة مقارنة بالزراعة الوحيدة. كان هذا مرتبطاً بانخفاض إجمالي لتثبيت N₂ عن طريق زراعة الفاصوليا ، لا سيما في تربة P العالية. ومع ذلك ، كان المعدل الأمثل لتثبيت النيتروجين أكبر في الزراعة البيئية منه في نظام الزراعة الوحيد حيث يكون الفسفور محدوداً في التربة. تم العثور على معظم فقدان الكربون من التربة بشكل أساسي عن طريق الكائنات الحية الدقيقة إلى الغلاف الجوي. حيث تم تصغيره بشكل كبير في الزراعة البيئية، من أجل تحسين كفاءة استخدام C عن طريق الكائنات الحية الدقيقة. تكشف هذه النتائج عن الارتباط القوي بين مخزون N و C ، مما يؤكد متانة معادلات MOMOS التي تمت صياغتها وفحصها حديثاً في هذه الورقة. أظهرت النمذجة الزراعية البيئية الحالية الدور الوظيفي للكتلة الحيوية الميكروبية ، في نمو المحصول المختلط وتفاعل التكافل ، من أجل التنبؤ بشكل أفضل بالتدفقات اليومية للتبادل C و N بين أعضاء النبات ومقصورات التربة والغلاف الجوي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: زراعة المشتركة؛ الكائنات الدقيقة؛ المتعايشين مع النبات؛ نماذج ميكانيكية؛ التبادل المستمر.

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Contents

I.	Introduction	11
II.	Bibliographic synthesis	14
II.1.	The intercropping system	14
II.2.	Resource sharing in intercropping system.....	14
II.2.1.	Complementarity	14
II.2.2.	The competition.....	15
II.2.3.	Facilitation.....	15
II.3.	Advantages of intercropping	16
II.3.1.	Efficient resource utilization and yield advantage.....	17
II.3.2.	Weed reduction.....	18
II.3.3.	Environmental impact	18
II.3.4.	The effects of pest and disease regulation	19
II.4.	Intercropping Inconvinients.....	20
II.5.	Effect of intercropping on the bioavailability of nitrogen	21
II.6.	Effect of intercropping on the bioavailability of carbon	21
II.7.	Effect of intercropping on phosphorus bioavailability	22
II.7.1.	The complementary use of phosphorus	22
II.7.2.	Phosphorus facilitation	23
II.8.	Cropping system modelling.....	24
II.8.1.	Crop system models	24
II.8.2.	Crop system models Typology	25
II.8.3.	Carbon and nitrogen modelling	26
II.8.4.	The decomposition models.....	27
III.	Material and methods	33
III.1.	MOMOS equation system and model parameterization.....	33
III.1.1.	Modelling production of plants	36
III.2.	Data collection.....	38
III.3.	Calculation tools.....	40
III.3.1.	VENSIM.....	40
III.4.	MOMOS Calibration process	40
III.4.1.	Calibration Payoffs Computation	41
III.4.2.	Optimization	41
III.4.3.	Computing Confidence Bounds.....	41
IV.	Results	42
IV.1.	Sahel estimation	42
IV.2.	The calibration results	44

IV.3.	Biomass production and transfer of C and N in the various organs of the plant	48
IV.4.	Transfer of C and N to microbial biomass	51
IV.5.	Transfer of C by total soil respiration.....	55
V.	Discussion	57
V.1.	Robustness of the model and the ecophysiological estimates	57
V.2.	Plant growth and grain yield.....	57
V.3.	Nodular growth and nitrogen uptake.....	59
V.4.	CN transfer between micro-organism – plant and atmosphere	60
VI.	Conclusion.....	62
VII.	Referenece.....	64

List of tables

Table 1: Physical and chemical soil properties of the experimental sites S1 and S2. Values represent the mean of 4 replicates \pm SE (standard errors).	39
Table 2: The R^2 between modelled and measured values and their respective p values at $p < 0.05$ for Maize and common bean under both intercropping and sole cropping system during the two growing seasons.....	43
Table 3: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil C compartments of the cropping systems in S1	46
Table 4: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil C compartments of the cropping systems in S2.....	47
Table 5: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil N compartments of the cropping systems in S1. Only the Values of N_{max}^j are measured on the site; the other values are optimised for the best prediction of the whole data set.	44
Table 6: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil N compartments of the cropping systems in S2. only the values of N_{max}^j measured on the site; the other values are optimised for the best prediction of the whole data set. Eq. are equation numbers in the text	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: The different interactions in the association system (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014).....	16
Figure 2 : MOMOS structure (Pansu et al., 2006).....	30
Figure 3: Localisation of the experimental sites (https://fr.wikipedia.org/).	39
Figure 4: Daily humidity modelled and measured in the surface layer of the soil wcl2 (a) that deeper wcl3 (b) under S1 conditions during the crop cycle conditions.....	42
Figure 5: Daily humidity modelled and measured in the surface layer of the soil wcl2 (a) that deeper wcl3 (b) under S2 conditions during the crop cycle conditions.....	43
Figure 6: The average air temperature for both sites during the cropping time.	43
Figure 7: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled aerial C stocks in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled aerial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.	49
Figure 8: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled aerial C stocks in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled aerial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.	50
Figure 9: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled nodular C stocks of the pure cropping and the intercropping in a) S1 c) S2. And modelled nodular N stocks of the pure cropping and the intercropping b) S1 d) S2.....	52
Figure 10: The cumulated N fixation for the sole crop and the intercropping in a) S1 b) S2	52
Figure 11: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled microbial C stocks in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled microbial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.	53
Figure 12: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled microbial C stocks in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled microbial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.	54
Figure 13: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled daily respiration in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean	55

Figure 13: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled daily respiration in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize c) common bean, and the intercropping b) maize f) common bean 55

Figure 14: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled daily respiration in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean 56

Preface

This work was done under the direction of Dr. LATATI Mourad, which was carried out in the Laboratory of Integrative Improvement of Plants Productions (AIPV: C2711100). Within the framework of three international projects of which Dr. LATATI is the leader:

ARIMNet 2-SEMIARID: Sustainable and efficient Mediterranean agricultural systems: improving the resilience of cropping systems through irrigation and diversification.

PRIMA-S1: CAMA: Participatory research-based approaches to adopting conservation agriculture in the Mediterranean region.

PRIMA-S2: BIODIVERSIFY: Stimulate ecosystem services thanks to Mediterranean agricultural systems with high biodiversity.

The objective of our work is to optimize the use of resources in Mediterranean production systems, and improve their resilience through the introduction of the concept of diversity; using the integrated multi-scale and multi-domain analysis approach, our goal is to assess the resilience of agricultural production systems in the Mediterranean with relation to their diversity of crops, water management, the structure of farms and the production strategy in order to assess whether they can maintain a high level of productivity and provision of ecosystem services in the face of climatic and socio-economic changes / shocks.

This work is a part of the LMD PhD thesis of Mr. KHERIF Omar in progress. The main goal of this thesis is to validate the model MOMOS for a complex cereal-legume intercropping system and to calibrate and parameterize it for a Mediterranean environment in a region characterized by calcareous soils and conditions low in phosphorus (P).

I. Introduction

The cereal production systems occupy an important place in the Algerian food supply. Still, they remain currently dependent on both pedoclimatic conditions and cropping system, which causes instability in agricultural production and its effects on farmer's income (Latati et al., 2016). The fallow-cereal rotation is the most used cropping system for cereal production in Algeria. It is widely practiced, covering more than 40% of arable land, but represents only less than 50% of the population's cereal needs (Alkama et al., 2009). Thus, replacing the current fallow-cereals farming system by the legume reintroduction will favor species diversity over time (in rotation with cereals and during fallow periods) and space (in intercropping), in order to enhance resource use efficiency. The agroecological intensification of the farming system based on high species diversification will then provide ecosystem services (Justes et al., 2017; Glaze-Corcoran et al., 2020). Legumes-cereals intercropping systems are more efficient in the use of nutrients resources (i.e. C, N and P) than current simplified systems (Latati et al., 2019). Furthermore, intercropping enhances functional complementarily, beneficial biological interactions, and synergies between plant species and micro-organisms within the agroecosystem, in both time and in-field space (Latati et al., 2017; Peoples et al., 2019). To better assess and estimate these intercropping performances in terms of resources use and storage (in particular C and N nutrients), the employment of integrated approach that incorporates analysis of empirical data and quantitative modelling of agroecological indicators were applied to link more deeply the C and N cycles (Gärdenäs et al., 2011; Todd-Brown et al., 2012; Latati et al., 2020). The modelling approach allows describing precisely the continuous exchange of C (e.g. Van der Heijden et al., 2008; Ibrahim et al., 2016) and N (e.g. Corre-Hellou et al., 2009; Pansu et al., 2018) resources between living organisms, soil and the atmosphere. The amount of soil organic matter (SOM) is one of the most key biogeochemical indicators that need to be assessed in a soil fertility analysis (Xu et al., 2013). The availability of C and N soil resources depends largely on the composition and structure of the microbial community; it is systematically linked with the growth stage of micro-organisms and the environmental conditions (Cotner et al., 2006; Sikorski, 2015; Latati et al., 2017). Among biological activities processes, micro-

organisms are considered a substantial source of bio-available C and N at either short or long term for crops (Tang *et al.*, 2014). However, crop systems can be managed over time (in rotation and during fallow periods) and space (intercropping and cover crop) to better enhance C-MB and N-MB stocks by introducing these sustainable management practices (Cong *et al.*, 2014; Blesh *et al.*, 2018). This underlines the complexity of C and N exchanges and the need of models to analyze deeply the C and N transfers between the living micro-organisms, the soil compartments and the atmosphere, especially in the case of intercropping systems. In the past decades, more than 250 models have been developed to describe biogeochemical processes in agroecosystems (Manzoni and Porporato, 2009). In contrast, only a few models were proposed to link the N and C cycles to the functional ecology of the plant-microorganisms systems (e.g. Pansu *et al.*, 2009, 2010, 2014, 2018; Jensen *et al.*, 2010; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2013, 2016; Latati *et al.*, 2019). The continuous exchanges of either C or N stocks were recently modelled for numerous crops cultivated in monoculture systems over either mid (e.g. Romanyaa *et al.*, 2000; Garten *et al.*, 2010) to long term periods (e.g. Palosuo *et al.*, 2012). Such C balance approaches excluded short-term modelling, and little data are available for legumes-cereals intercropping system (e.g. Corre-Hellou *et al.*, 2009; Sikorski, 2015; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016; Pansu *et al.*, 2018). In the last ten years, MOMOS (Modelling Organic transformations by Micro-Organisms of Soils) model was one of the most mechanist's short-term models that have been proposed for simulating daily and continuous exchanges of C and N flows between plant organs and symbionts, decomposer micro-organisms, atmosphere and soil compartments. The MOMOS versions (2 to 6) are the last developed versions, which are modified from the initial MOMOS-C (Sallih and Pansu, 1993) and MOMOS-N (Pansu *et al.*, 1998) models. They are developed based on studies using isotopic tracers (^{14}C and ^{15}N) from controlled laboratory conditions to field conditions (soil bag). MOMOS use the same conceptual approach, which was centered on the functional role of the soil microbial biomass (Pansu *et al.*, 2009). However, the evolution of MOMOS versions has passed through different formulation in term of model complexity compartmental definition, biogeochemical processes and levels of parameterization. The MOMOS C microbial core was calibrated in dry Bolivian puna and moister Venezuelan paramo (Pansu *et al.*, 2004) then validated in six tropical sites over a

wide range of altitudes and climates (Pansu et al., 2010) the extended to the N cycle (Pansu et al.,2014). More recently, the MOMOS model was extended to link microbial transformations to plant growth and validated on data bases collected from field experiments performed in cereals-legumes intercropping system (faba bean-durum wheat) in French Mediterranean conditions to simulate the continuous exchanges of C (Ibrahim et al., 2016) and N (Pansu et al., 2018) between the plant organs, the living micro-organisms, the soil compartments and the atmosphere (Latati et al., 2020). This thesis aims to extend these studies to simulate the continuous C and N exchanges between the compartments integrated into the last version of MOMOS (Pansu et al., 2018) by using an update one included new equation and new parameters proposed and suggested based on the previous studies .So our objectives were to:

- I. Optimize the equations system for plant growth (within some new mathematical formulations) as a new tool to simulate the daily C and N exchanges between plant symbionts, microbial biomass, soil and atmosphere using data base collected previously from two farmers plots under calcareous low P-soils,
- II. Parameterize and validate the MOMOS model at two contrasted pedoclimatic conditions (site 1 and site 2), highlighting the collected data from summer intercropping system (common bean-maize) during two successive growing seasons.
- III. Estimate values of daily microbial C and N exchanged from decomposer micro-organisms within the C loss by soil respiration, and simultaneously to estimate essential parameters of C and N flows for plant and nodule growth and the daily amount of N fixed by common bean nodular symbionts.

II. Bibliographic synthesis

II.1. The intercropping system

The intercropping system is defined as a system with two or more crops with complementary growth cycles developed simultaneously in the same field (Vandermeer et al., 1998). The combination of crops can include: annual plants with annual plants, annual plants with perennial plants and perennial plants with perennial plants (Eskandari and Ghanbari, 2009). According to Lithourgi et al., (2011); malezieux et al., (2009), intercropping can be divided into:

- **Row intercropping:** Grow two or more crops simultaneously in regular rows. One or more crops may sow simultaneously and alternately or may randomly arrange in the rows.
- **Mixed intercropping:** Cultivate two or more crops simultaneously without following a regular arrangement of rows. This type of intercropping is desirable for legume-fodder crop associations in pastoral systems.
- **Strip intercropping:** consists in cultivating two or more cultures in distinct bands and wide enough to allow independent cultivation, but narrow enough to favor interactions
- **Relay intercropping:** Cultivate two or more crops during part of the life cycle of each one. However, the second crop is planted after the first has reached the reproductive stage, but before it is ready to harvest.

II.2. Resource sharing in intercropping system

In comparison with a homogeneous pure cropping system, the different species that share a common space interact with each other and between the environments in different ways (Malezieux et al., 2009):

II.2.1. Complementarity

They occur when plants with complementary traits found in association interact positively to increase productivity (brooker et al., 2015), thanks to the partitioning of resources whose species can use different types of resources (for example, the different

forms of nitrogen) or different amounts (e.g., water, light) or different time or space (Fridley, 2001). In ecological terms, resource complementarity minimizes the niche overlap and the competition between crop species, and permits crops to capture a greater range and quantity of resources than the sole crops (Lithourgi et al., 2011).

II.2.2. The competition

Competition is the process in which two individual plants or two populations of plants interact so that at least one has a negative effect on the other (Vandermeer, 1989). It is a determining mechanism for the structure and dynamics of the plant community. The agronomic advantages of multispecies systems are the result of differences in the competitive ability for growth factors between plant components (malezieux et al., 2009); they occur when the component cultures do not compete for the same ecological niches and when the interspecific competition for a given resource is weaker than the intraspecific competition (Lithourgi et al., 2011).

II.2.3. Facilitation

Is the process in which two individual plants or two populations of plants interact in such a way that one has a positive effect on the other (malezieux et al., 2009; Hauggaard-Nielsen and Jensen, 2005), either by providing a limiting resource or by improving the environmental conditions of the other species (Bybee-Finley and Rayn, 2018).

Facilitation can occur through direct mechanisms such as Transfer of nitrogen (N) fixed from legumes to non-legumes found in association, the improving of nutrients availability, change the soil pH , Indirect: like the reduction of the damage induced by weeds, pests and diseases (Hauggaard-Nielsen and Jensen, 2005), the change in the architecture of the roots (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014) .

Figure 1:The different interactions in the association system (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014).

II.3. Advantages of intercropping

Intercropping is widespread, particularly in countries with high amounts of subsistence agriculture and low amounts of agricultural mechanization. In some regions, intercropping has been - and remains - the dominant form of agriculture (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). This system has been known for a long time, a quantitative evaluation suggests that 89% of cowpeas in Africa are intercropped, 90% of common beans in Colombia are intercropped, 73% in Guatemala, 80% in Brazil and the total percentage of cultivated land actually devoted to intercropping varies from 17% in India to 94% in Malawi (Vandermeer, 1989). Farmers in Latin America produce 70-90% of their beans intercropped with maize, potatoes and other crops (Lithourgi *et al.*, 2011). Recently, several studies have been carried out on this system to demonstrate the advantages it offers:

II.3.1. Efficient resource utilization and yield advantage

Liebig's 'law of the minimum' suggests that crop production is determined by the lack of a single critical resource – the limiting factor. If a cropping system increases the availability of a limiting resource then yield should increase (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). In many agricultural systems, the limiting factors are nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) or water availability, whilst cropping season length is often restricted by daylight and temperature extremes (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). Intercropping can increase phytoavailability and acquisition of limiting resources, and management of root/rhizosphere interactions can improve resource-use efficiency by crops (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014; Latati *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2010) which is always associated with a high yield of seeds and the biomass will be greater than that of monoculture. For example, In a soil where phosphorus is a limiting factor, Latati *et al.*, (2013,2016,2018) have reported that maize combined with common bean causes very high seed and biomass yields, thanks to the mechanisms of complementarity, facilitation and interspecies competition between these species (Latati *et al.*, 2016). They confirmed these benefits in the intercropping of maize / cowpea (Latati *et al.*, 2014).

Where water is the main limitation, intercropping is often increased water availability or efficient use of available resources attributed mainly to better acquisition of water in the soil profile through root distributions complementary (Xu *et al.*, 2008).

In many studies have proven these benefits with different conditions; 79% of experiments on biodiversity, biomass production in systems with various species was 1.7 times higher on average than in monoculture (Cardinale *et al.*, 2007). The increase in the yield of cereals under the effect of the intercropping with legumes is reported in the literature in maize when it is cultivated in association with faba bean (Li *et al.*, 2007; Kaci *et al.*, 2018). Cowpea (Eskandari, 2012; Li *et al.*, 2005); or in wheat when intercropped with faba beans (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2013), common beans (Li *et al.*, 2008), soybeans (Zhang and Li, 2003), chickpeas (Betencourt, 2012) or in barley intercropped with peas, faba beans and lupines (Hauggaard-Nielsen *et al.*, 2008).

II.3.2. Weed reduction

Weed control is an important aspect in intercropping since chemical control is difficult once crops have emerged (Lithourgi and *al.*, 2011). Combination crops reduce the risk of weeds; they often lead to a reduction in the density and growth of weeds compared to monocrops. According to Liebman and Dyck, (1993), there are two types of actions identified to explain this reduction:

- Competition for resources (water, light, nutrients): it is more observed when cultivated species are complementary in the assimilation of resources (Malézieux and *al.*, 2009; Poggio, 2005).
- All allelopathic effects: refers to the inhibition of plant growth by chemical compounds which are released into the soil by neighboring plants (Nair, 1993).

On the other hand, intercrops may provide yield advantages without suppressing the growth of weeds below levels observed in sole crops if intercrops use resources that are not exploitable by weeds (Liebman and Dyck, 1993). Several studies have proven these benefits; the Intercropping of sorghum with fodder cowpea intercepted more light, captured greater quantities of macronutrients N, P, and K, produced higher crop yields, and contained lower weed densities and less weed dry matter compared with sole-cropped sorghum (Abraham and Singh, 1984). Cultivated pea associated with barley had a greater competitive capacity against weeds and inorganic soil nitrogen was therefore used for the production of barley grain instead of the biomass of weeds (Hauggaard-Nielsen *et al.*, 2001).

II.3.3. Environmental impact

Intercropping system can provide environmental services that have impacts beyond the field scale, either spatially or temporally (Malézieux *et al.*, 2009):

II.3.3.1. The impact on biodiversity

The intercropping of compatible species promotes biodiversity: plants with insects, birds with mammals, above or below the ground (Lithourgidis *et al.*, 2011; Perfecto *et al.*, 2003). Greater biodiversity can have local effects, such as greater

resilience to abiotic or biotic disturbance factors, in particular through greater microbial diversity (Altieri, 1999).

Song *et al.*, (2007) found that the rhizospheric communities of wheat, maize and faba bean did not differ and were more affected by soil type than by plant species. During the intercropping of these, significant differences in the composition of the communities were observed between the intercrops of wheat- faba bean and wheat -maize, and compared to their sole crop. New species have been found in the rhizosphere of faba bean intercropped with maize which may explain the increase in yield (Zhang *et al.*, 2010). However, Schmidt *et al.*, (2001) found between one and five other earthworm species in the wheat / clover intercropping.

II.3.3.2. Impact on soil conservation and water quality

The intercropping shows positive impacts on soil structure conservation by reducing the risk of soil erosion, particularly in agroforestry systems (Wang *et al.*, 2011). This advantage is probably linked to its effects on biotic factors and the different OM inputs (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014).

In addition, as mineral fertilizers have contributed to environmental damage such as pollution of groundwater induced by nitrate leaching (Bybee-Finley and Ryan, 2018). Thanks to the capacity of the biological fixation of atmospheric nitrogen, the intercropped legumes are considered as an alternative and sustainable way for nitrogen supply (Fustec *et al.*, 2010). A three-year study in China on the intercropping in strips with sweet maize and soybeans showed a reduction of 39.8% of the mineral nitrogen of the soil compared to the monocrop of maize (Tang *et al.*, 2017).

II.3.4. The effects of pest and disease regulation

An important aspect of the association systems is its ability to reduce the incidence of parasites and diseases (Rämert, 2002). Several mechanisms combine to allow a sustainable protection of crops against specialized fungal pathogens (Trenbath, 1993).

Mixed crop species can also delay the onset of diseases by reducing the spread of disease carrying spores and by modifying environmental conditions so that they are less

favourable to the spread of certain pathogen (Lithourgi et al., 2011). Vilich-Meller, (1992) has shown that mixtures of winter rye / winter wheat and spring barley / oats reduce fungal leaf diseases. A significant reduction in the frequency and intensity of diseases especially for *Erysiphe graminis* f.sp. *hordei* and *Puccinia recondita* f.sp. *tritici* but also included leaf spot diseases caused by *Drechslera avenae* and *Rhynchosporium secalis*.

This system can promote the abundance of natural enemies of pests (Lithourgi et al., 2011). An analysis of 209 studies involving 287 pest species, Compared to monoculture the pest population was lower in 52% of the studies (149 espèces) and higher in 15% (44 species) and The natural enemy population of pests was higher in the associated crop in 53% of the studies and lower in 9% (Andow, 1991). Combined cultivation of maize with soybeans, peanuts and common beans significantly reduces termite attack which is the consequence of a loss of maize grain yield compared to their single crop, while increasing nesting of ant predators in maize fields (Sekamatte et al., 2003).

II.4. Intercropping Inconvinients

Depending on the mixed crops, competition for light, water and nutrients, or allelopathic effects that occur between mixed crops can reduce yields (Santalla et al., 2001; Olowe and Adeyemo, 2009). According to Lithourgi et al., (2011) the disadvantages of the associated culture are:

- The difficulty of management, especially where there is a high degree of mechanization or when the crops making up different requirements for fertilizers, herbicides and Pesticides.
- Additional cost for the separation of mixed grains and lack of marketing of mixed grains.
- Problems with harvesting due to lodging and loss of grain.
- Mechanization is the major problem in associated farming. The machines used for sowing, weeding, fertilizing and harvesting are made for uniform fields. Harvesting remains a big problem, but this can be more easily

overcome where the intercropped crops are harvested for fodder or pasture.

II.5. Effect of intercropping on the bioavailability of nitrogen

The dynamics and absorption of nutrients is the most studied domain in multi-crop systems. Interactions between physical, biological and chemical processes in the rhizosphere affect how nutrients are cycled differently in intercropping, compared to monoculture (Ehrmann and Ritz, 2014). The common bean when intercropped with maize shows positive interactions leading to an improvement in the concentration of nitrogen in the rhizosphere of common bean via atmospheric nitrogen fixation, and as a consequence the assimilation of Nitrogen increases (Latati et al., 2013, 2017, 2018). Same result was observed in the intercropping of peas / oats (Neumann et al., 2007). Hauggaard-Nielsen et al., (2001) found that 90 to 95% of the total amount of nitrogen accumulated is derived from the biological fixation of nitrogen in the intercropping of peas / barley. In their other study, they showed that the availability of nitrogen in the soil was higher in pea, common bean and lupine when they intercropped with barley compared to their unique crops (Hauggaard-Nielsen et al., 2008). These results are also observed when faba bean is found in intercropping with maize or wheat (Cong et al., 2014). Other study proves that the bacteria responsible for denitrification (bacteria oxidizing ammonia) are more important in the mixed crops plots which increases the availability of nitrate in the maize and wheat rhizosphere compared to their unique crop (Song et al., 2007). In addition, other advantages of the combination of cereal - legume which corresponds in the transfer of nitrogen between these two crops. Xiao et al., (2004) reported that 15% of the total N uptake by wheat comes from faba bean which shows the positive interaction between these two species.

II.6. Effect of intercropping on the bioavailability of carbon

In plant-soil systems, enzymes derived from microorganisms, plants and animal residues play an important role in the breakdown of organic matter and the nutrient cycle (Zarea et al., 2011). Mixed crops, with different plant species and specific functional groups, such as nitrogen-fixing legumes, affect the abundance, activity and composition

of soil enzymes and decomposer communities and therefore soil organic carbon increases (Zarea *et al.*, 2009). Studies on the soybean-maize intercropping revealed that these had little influence on SOC levels with a significant increase in the carbon stock in microbial biomass compared to monocrops (Oelbermann and Echarte, 2010).

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from the soil surface are indicators of the overall activity of soil microorganisms and the root-nodule symbiosis. A significant increase in soil respiration was found in the association of cowpeas / maize compared to their single crop (Latati *et al.*, 2014). This result has also been demonstrated in the common bean / maize combination (Latati *et al.*, 2017, 2018), where the contribution of C to the soil through the root residues for both legumes and cereals, was found to be higher in intercropping than in the sole crop. On the other hand, the rhizosphere of the mixed crop common bean has shown an even more pronounced increase in the carbon stock in microbial biomass which was strongly correlated with C nodules. These advantages are also reported in the intercropping of durum wheat / chickpeas and durum wheat / lentil (Tang *et al.*, 2014). However, another study on the intercropping of durum wheat and faba bean shows greater root respiration in wheat than in faba bean in the intercropped plots and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from these two crops were more important in their association than in their sole crops (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2013).

II.7. Effect of intercropping on phosphorus bioavailability

Phosphorus is a limited plant nutrient and very immobile. It is often found in fixed organic compounds or in the form of Ca phosphates and Fe and Al phosphates, which are not directly extractable by plants (Bertrand *et al.*, 2003). Several plants have developed mechanisms by which soil P can be mobilized in forms which can then be used by them and by plants growing nearby, so that the roots can interact (Zhang *et al.*, 2004). The mechanisms by which the P cycle and plant uptake are affected by multi-crop arrangements include complementary use of P and facilitation of P (Li *et al.*, 2007)

II.7.1. The complementary use of phosphorus

Different plant species have developed different adaptations to mobilise and access different forms of soil P, complementary of P use can be exploited within

multiple-crop system (Li *et al.*, 2007). Access to different P pools due to the exudation of organic acid which reduces competition between plants in the mixed system, such effects have been found in the intercropping of common bean / wheat (Li *et al.*, 2007).

It is possible to acquire more P in associated crops than in monoculture, simply by increasing the length and density of the roots, or due to differences in growth and rooting patterns, and by accessing different pools of phosphorus in the soil (Li *et al.*, 2007 ; Plassard *et al.*, 2015), when the maize plant is intercropped with the peanut, they had access to a greater number of soil phosphorus sources, different from those of the peanuts and maize in the sole crop, due to a combination of occupation of a large volume of soil, complementary P and peanut facilitation (El Dessougi *et al.*, 2003).

II.7.2. Phosphorus facilitation

Phosphorus facilitation describes the mechanisms by which a plant can increase the uptake of phosphorus by another plant. In this sense, changes in pH in the rhizosphere are a powerful way for determining the availability of inorganic forms of P (Hinsinger, 2001).

Legumes studies have shown that phosphorus facilitation is due to the decrease in rhizosphere pH following a phosphorus deficiency in the soil (Houassine *et al.*, 2019) and this change in pH can be significantly higher in the cereal -legume intercropping compared to the monocrop (Latati *et al.*, 2014). This mechanism demonstrated in the combination of maize / chickpea (Betencourt *et al.*, 2012), common bean / maize (Latati *et al.*, 2013, 2017, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2007) where the increase of the availability of P in the maize rhizosphere was explained by the acidification of the legume rhizosphere (Betencourt *et al.*, 2012). In other words, the decrease in pH of the legume rhizosphere could be directly linked to an imbalance in the production of H⁺ proton with the O₂ consumed by the nodules for N₂ fixation (Alkama *et al.*, 2012). Wheat increased proton release by 36% from common beans in their intercropping plots compared with the sole crop (Li *et al.*, 2007). For maize mixed with legumes, this can lead to alkalization of the rhizosphere if the calcium was not absorbed by the maize (Betencourt *et al.*, 2012). Latati *et al.*, (2014) have demonstrated this positive interaction between pH and Ca when

maize has been intercropped with cowpea and proved the advantage of combinations for improving the availability of phosphorus.

Inal *et al.*, (2007) have proven another mechanism of phosphorus facilitation via the secretion of phosphatase which is responsible for the mobilization of organic phosphorus, it was strongly liberated in the intercropping of peanut / maize compared to their unique culture, this is in agreement with studies including on the intercropping of chickpeas with wheat (Wang *et al.*, 2007).

In calcareous soils, several studies have shown that the facilitation of P between mixed cereal-legume crops has occurred not only by decreasing the pH of the rhizosphere but by exudation of organic acid, it is more produced by the intercropped legume. This mechanism was illustrated in the association of maize / faba bean (Li *et al.*, 2007), blé /lupin (Cu *et al.*, 2005).

II.8. Cropping system modelling

II.8.1. Crop system models

To better understand and follow the spatio-temporal evolutions of socio-environmental phenomena affected by global changes and provide useful information for the management of territories, it is crucial to have methods and tools adapted both in terms of speed and ease of data acquisition and deployment potential over large spaces (Fargette *et al.*, 2017).

The analysis of culture systems can follow the experimental path, which is considered to be the number 1 tool for responding to certain research problems, but may well be the worst method for responding to them due to experimental errors and the variability of the behavior of each genotype in different environments. Although, our current knowledge is often poor for detailed processes (Brisson, 2009); Consequently, conducting an experiment becomes difficult, expensive in terms of time and money with the increase in the scale of study since it requires several years of experience to be significant. In similar situations, the use of culture models becomes interesting in the sense that it will reduce the number of experiments while distributing an answer to the question studied (Belhouchette, 2004).

Crop modelling in agricultural research has evolved over the past 20 years from a marginal activity often criticized by many agronomists to a tool commonly used in research and become an essential tool that allows you to know, understand, invent and share new ways of producing (Robertson and Carberry, 2010).

According to Hadria *et al.*, (2010), Crop models represent the interactions between the soil, the plant and the atmosphere in order:

- To predict the production of biomass and its distribution in the various organs of the plant and in particular in the grains.
- To simulate the response of a crop to environmental stresses (eg: drought) or to various agronomic routes.
- Analyze the impact of crops and farming practices on the environment (agricultural pollution, water use, etc.).

Furthermore, cropping systems require a model capable of simulating not only the functioning of a specific crop but also the development of different plants cultivated in rotation or in association while always taking pedo-climatic variations (Belhouchette, 2004; Stockle *et al.*, 2003), some models are appear to meet this need such as WOFOST (Supit, 1994), CropSyst (Stöckle *et al.*, 2003), APSIM (McCown *et al.*, 1996), DSSAT (Jones *et al.*, 2003), EPIC (Williams *et al.*, 1989), STICS (Brisson *et al.*, 1998). Where the application of these models on a regional scale would provide answers to certain questions posed by agricultural and environmental managers (Hadria *et al.*, 2010).

II.8.2. Crop system models Typology

A model is a simplified representation of reality which makes it possible to provide information without going through real experiments. In addition, there are necessarily 3 components to the crop models: complexity, degree of calculation and scale of application (Rossitier, 2003).

The combination of these 3 components allows the classification of models of cropping systems. Complexity refers to the detail with which the processes are made explicit in the model; we distinguish from empirical models where the processes are not known, but where the relationships are established on the basis of experience (Rossitier, 2003). And mechanistic models that rely on a representation of the mechanisms that

govern the dynamics in a system, using an approach based on the “first principles” (eg starting from the most fundamental hypotheses) to build a predictive model (Godard, 2015). By the degree of calculation they are classified into qualitative models with quantitative models refer to the accuracy of the prediction of the model. Finally, the most mechanistic and quantitative models are generally applied on a smaller scale (Rossitier, 2003). Based on the field of application of the models we can distinguish:

i. **Eco-physiological models:** models that are based on a detailed description of eco-physiological processes. The first eco-physiological models simulated only the carbon cycle then they became more complex to be dynamic, capable of adopting a daily time step and integrating photosynthesis, respiration, decomposition like the MOMOS model or the Roth C model (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996), The energy balance and the water balance, such is the case of the WOFST model (Van Diepen *et al.*, 1989).

ii. **Agronomic models:** are predominantly mechanical models whose cultural practices are introduced to the physiological notions characteristic of the crop and which allows the forecasting of yields like the stics model (Brisson *et al.*, 1998) or APSIM (McCown *et al.*, 1996).

iii. At the same time, agro-environmental concerns are becoming stronger and call for the development of other models: **agro-environmental models.**

EPIC (Williams *et al.*, 1989) is set to simulate the impact of soil erosion, pollution and climate change on agricultural production and again CropSyst (Stöckle *et al.*, 2003) which simulates both erosion, nitrogen leaching as well as nitrogen losses by incomplete volatilization and denitrification

iv. **Environmental models:** their objective is to study the transfer of materials in the environment (migration, dexivation, mineralization, transport of nitrates or other pollutants), from plot to watersheds such as DAISY (Hansen *et al.*, 1990) or PASTIS (Lafolie, 1991).

II.8.3. Carbon and nitrogen modelling

The upper layers of the earth contain the largest reserves of organic carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) potentially available for plant growth (Batjes, 1996). Understanding their cycles - that is to say, the states under which they are encountered and the

biochemical processes that cause them to pass from one state to another - is necessary. Given the complexity of these cycles and their interactions, their modelling is an essential step (Pansu, 2006).

Manzoni and Porporato, (2009) examined and classified around 250 different mathematical models developed over 80 years. Most of the models currently available are from initial efforts to provide a mathematical description of biogeochemical processes in soils. According to Batlle-Aguilar *et al.*, (2011), these models represent the interactions between the soil, the plant and the atmosphere in the main objective are numerous, for example:

- i. Understanding and forecasting feedback between terrestrial ecosystems and global climate (for example, estimating and predicting the climatological and biological effects of human activities).
- ii. Influence of climate change on the nutrient cycle in soils.
- iii. Prediction of changes in soil C and N cycles linked to possible changes in land use.
- iv. Forecasts of crop productivity and of the system's response to specific physical changes in the soil.

In addition To better understand the dynamics of N and C in Mediterranean soils, mechanistic models can answer several relevant questions (Latati *et al.*, 2019). They allow, for example, distinguishing compartments of plant origin generally located in coarse fractions of the soil, or of microbial origin rather located in finer fractions (Pansu *et al.*, 2009).

Pansu *et al.*, (2010) added that the main objective of modelling soil carbon and nitrogen was the possibility of improving the availability of nutrients for plants without reducing their storage in the soil, especially their inorganic phase for the preservation of the soil, environment and health.

II.8.4. The decomposition models

Appreciation the formation and renewal of organic soil stocks is an important objective, in particular in the context of changes in land use (deforestation, agricultural abandonment, amendments, fertilization, mechanized cultivation, etc.).

Organic matter is one of the main keys to maintaining sustainable agriculture (Pansu, 2006). Numerical tools are increasingly used to understand the changes induced in ecosystems. It was found that the understanding of the coupled dynamics N and C a paramount importance for the models predictive of the evolution of the MOS (Pansu, 2006).

If the microbial biomass is still considered as the decomposition agent, we can distinguish on the basis of the internal structure of the models which describe the dynamics of the MOS, the models which take it explicitly into account as one or more compartments, and those which take it into account only indirectly in the values of the decomposition speed constants (Pansu *et al.*, 2006). Surprisingly, most of the proposed soil organic matter decomposition models use linear modelling approaches that do not explicitly include the specific functions of microorganisms in the equations of the decomposition process (Pansu *et al.*, 2010), and the parameters are not linked to the environment variables (Pansu *et al.*, 2009). Then other mechanistic models do not allow to predict the continuous transfers of C between plants, soils and atmosphere since they mainly focus on total C without considering the role of microorganisms (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016, Allison *et al.*, 2010) or the relationship with nitrogen (Pansu *et al.*, 2009). For example: the stics model (Brisson *et al.*, 1998), the Roth C model (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996) MOMOS-1 (Sallih and Pansu 1993; Pansu *et al.*, 1998), or CO2Fix (Masera *et al.*, 2003)...ect. On the other hand, the complexity of the nitrogen cycle requires models which precisely describe the mineralization processes and the immobilization of nitrogen associated with the evolution of microbial biomass and organic substrate (Pansu *et al.*, 2009).

Thanks to in situ incubation experiments using ^{14}C and ^{14}N isotopic tracers, Pansu *et al.*, (2004) compared five alternatives models; they conclude that the best one is that whose considers MB as the center of the decomposition processes. They proposed a new model: MOMOS (Modelling Organic transformation by Micro-organisms of the soil).

II.8.4.1. MOMOS

It is a mechanistic model which is based on the ecological function of microbial biomass (Latati *et al.*, 2019), in particular that of prokaryotes which play an essential role in the ecological functions relating to the decomposition and fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (Sikorski, 2015) and even for fungi in cold and humid areas where the C: N ratio of BM decreases significantly during decomposition (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016). It is also the first model whose parameters are only first-order decay rates (Pansu, 2006), it was designed to limit the parameters mainly to kinetic rates of compartment decomposition (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016).

The model simulates their growth, respiration and mortality as the main factors in the mineralization and humification processes of organic substrates (Pansu *et al.*, 2010). This model was really related to the commonly accepted image of the organic cycle: (i) plant biomass is supplied by atmospheric carbon dioxide and mineral nitrogen from the soil during the photosynthesis process (ii) this biomass restores C and N to the soil in two ways: by exudation of labile metabolites and by senescence of labile and stable necromass (iii) exits from the various compartments of plant or microbial origin feeds BM (iv) microbial respiration feeds the CO₂ sink to the atmosphere (v) microbial mortality produces metabolites again consumed by BM or stabilized in the humus (Pansu *et al.*, 2004, 2006). The only process that is supposed to be more physico-chemical than biological is the maturation of the humus from HL to HS (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016).

II.8.4.2. Structure of MOMOS

MOMOS is close to linear models in its structure. However, only the expression of microbial respiration is non-linear: it is a quadratic function of the pool of microbial biomass squared (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016). It is therefore composed of five compartments of which the microbial biomass is the center of exchanges between the different flows of the compartments of fresh OM (stable and labile necromass) and those of stable and labile humus.

In addition, MOMOS can be coupled with various models of agricultural or natural production as well as various models of soil physics and water:

SAHEL soil water management model (Penning de Vries et al., 1989) makes it possible to estimate daily soil moisture from climatic data (max and min temperature, wind speed, sunshine, etc.).

TAO (Transformation of Added Organic materials): model was designed to estimate the fractions of labile and stable necromass taken up by the MB (Ibrahim et al., 2016).

FAPROM model for primary fallow production (Martineau and Saugier, 2006), its coupling with MOMOS makes it possible to understand and predict the return of nitrogen fertility by the fallow, thus emerging as a forecasting tool essential for ecosystem sustainability (Pansu et al., 2006).

Figure 2 : MOMOS structure (Pansu et al., 2006).

II.8.4.3. MOMOS evolution

MOMOS have started as five-compartment named MOMOS-2 developed for the prediction of cycle C (Sallih and Pansu, 1993) and N (Pansu et al., 1998) from studies of isotopic tracers under controlled laboratory conditions. MOMOS-2 served as a starting point for study in natural conditions in Venezuela (pansu et al., 2006). It describes the flow of materials of plant origin distributed in: - a microbial compartment BM for a P_{MB} fraction, - a humus labile compartment HL for a P_{HL} fraction, - a stable humified compartment for a P_{HS} fraction. MOMOS-2 therefore had 8 parameters including 5 first order decay rates k_{VL} , k_{VS} , k_{MB} , k_{HL} , k_{HS} (dimension t^{-1}) linked to temperature and humidity by laws deriving from chemical kinetics and 3 dimensionless parameters type r of stream sharing: P_{MB} , P_{HL} , P_{HS} (pansu et al., 2006).

MOMOS-3 results from the simplification of MOMOS-2, proposes a grouping of humified compartments HL and HS in a single humic compartment H. Its formulation is equivalent to that of the Roth-C model (Jenkinson, 1990).

Thirdly, Pansu et al., (2004) have tested the validity of a simplification of MOMOS-3 / Roth-C into MOMOS-4 by suppressing the renewal from the decomposition of microbial materials therefore the recycling part of H and MB compartments are removed.

The equation system of MOMOS-5 is similar to that of the CANDY model (Franko et al., 1995) and to that used by Sagggar et al., (1996) established to calculate 14C turnover and residence times in soils (Pansu et al., 2004). However, MOMOS-5 differs from the former models in the following aspects: (i) fractionation of NC inputs into VL and VS, (ii) change of kinetic calculation of the microbial respiration through modelling the microbial respiratory quotient q_{CO_2} by connecting it to the variations in BM (the respiration of microorganisms increases in proportion to their growth) and to the respiration rate k_{resp} (dimension t^{-1}), thereby introducing a term of non-linearity, and (iii) elimination of the flow fractionation between necromass and MB used in CANDY (in MOMOS-5 the whole flow from the NC substrate enters into MB)(Pansu et al., 2004; Pansu et al., 2006).

MOMOS-6 attempts to improve MOMOS-5 by introducing a stable humus compartment (HS) that results from the slow maturation of HL and supplies the dormant MB with maintenance energy, when the fresh C input is exhausted (Pansu *et al.*, 2009).

However, MOMOS-5 and -6 are only regulated by first-order kinetic constants related to climate and other environmental conditions... (K parameters, dimension t^{-1}), without the dimensionless parameters (efficiency factors) often used in SOM models to fractionate the flows between the compartments (in MOMOS-2 to -4, or, e.g and more generally of all the other compartment models in the literature) (Pansu *et al.*, 2004; Pansu *et al.*, 2009).

The model calibrated on two altitude systems, the Venezuelan paramo and the puna Boliviennea where it was validated on six highly contrasted ecosystems with a tropical altitudinal gradient, and thanks to in situ incubation experiments with isotopic tracers ^{14}C et ^{15}N , it is established that for inputs of quality, the only variables regulating the dynamics of decomposition are temperature, humidity and microbial respiration rate (k_{resp}) related to the properties of the soil (Pansu *al.*, 2006; Pansu *et al.*, 2009).

No application to complex open systems with regular flows has yet been published until its validation under Mediterranean conditions with the intercropping of durum wheat / faba bean cultivated in France in the agro-ecosystem of Mauguio. The results showed the possibility of using it in a wide range of terrestrial environments (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016). They have also demonstrated that MOMOS is perfectly suited to studying the dynamics of nitrogen and carbon in Mediterranean soils, the model made it possible to predict the daily exchanges of C and N between the different organs of the plant, the soil and the atmosphere, by modelling the functional role of microorganisms, in particular rhizobial N_2 -fixing bacteria (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016; Pansu *et al.*, 2018).

III. Material and methods

III.1. MOMOS equation system and model parameterization

The published models were over-parameterized, two thirds of them needed parameters not linked to environmental variables, a third did not explicitly use a microbial compartment and none of them really considered the functional role of microorganism (Pansu *et al.*, 2009). MOMOS is also the first model whose parameters are only first order decay rates (Pansu, 2006), it is only parameterized by seven speed constants (the dimension is (d^{-1}) which are linked to the quality organic inputs (Bottner *et al.*, 2006), soil texture (Pansu *et al.*, 2007), soil moisture and temperature. It is probably one of the most sensitive models to climate change, as shown by the general non linear equation (Hammoudi *et al.*, 2014):

$$1. \quad \dot{x} = f(T)f(\Theta)Ax + B$$

X is the variable vector representing the concentration of C and N in the five model compartments (aerial and root biomass, microbial biomass, necromass, stable humus and labile humus) (Latati *et al.*, 2019).and \dot{x} is the vector of the derivatives of x. A: is the model parameter matrix for each organic element and B is a vector determining the external C and N inputs.

$f(T)$: is an exponential function of temperature: (Pansu *et al.*, 2004, 2010; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016) .

$$2. \quad f(T) = Q_{10}^{(T-T_{opt})/10}$$

Where T is the actual daily soil temperature (0–10 cm layer) set equal to air temperature; T_{opt} is the optimal decomposition temperature settled at 28°C, a temperature often used to perform laboratory decomposition experiments under optimal conditions (Thuriès *et al.*, 2001 ; Pansu *et al.*, 2010) Q_{10} is the difference in rate for a temperature increase of 10 °C, fixed at 2.2(Pansu *et al.*, 2010) and $f(\Theta)$:is the soil water function normalized to the water holding capacity WHC (Pansu *et al.*, 2010 ; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016)

$$3. \quad f(\Theta) = \text{MIN} \left(\frac{\theta}{\text{WHC}}, 1 \right).$$

The soil moisture (θ) was simulated by coupling MOMOS with the SAHEL model (Penning de Vries *et al.*, 1989), which has a simplified version using data from daily maximum and minimum temperature, but in this study we have used an update one taking into account the wind speed and the water vapor pressure, the rainfall, solar radiation. These data have been collected from the ONM station in the Setif region. In addition to some physical soil parameters including soil moisture measured at each growth stage from two layers (0-15) and (15-30).

As carbon and nitrogen are closely associated in living organisms, Pansu *et al.*, (2014) proposed to model the MOMOS-N nitrogen cycle in the same way as the MOMOS-C carbon cycle (Pansu *et al.*, 2010).

For MOMOS-C carbon the model matrix A_C is:

$$4. \begin{bmatrix} -k_{VL} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_{VS} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k_{VL} & k_{VS} & -(q_{CO_2} + k_{MB}) & k_{HL} & k_{HS} \\ 0 & 0 & k_{MB} & -(k_{HL} + k_{HLS}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & k_{HLS} & k_{HS} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where the central term of A_C defines microbial respiration.

q_{CO_2} represent the metabolic quotient of MB:

$$5. q_{CO_2} = k_{resp} \frac{x_{MB}}{C_{MB}^0}$$

C_{MB}^0 is an estimate of the biomass at steady state. k_{resp} is the respiration coefficient (day^{-1}) adjusted to the 0–20 μm soil textural fraction (F_{0-20}) (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016):

$$6. k_{resp} = 0.0008 F_{0-20} + 0.062$$

And for MOMOS-N carbon the model matrix A_N is:

$$7. \begin{bmatrix} -k_{VL} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_{VS} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k_{VL} & k_{VS} & -(f(x_{C,MB}, x_{N,MB})/f(T)f(\theta)x_{N,MB} + k_{MB}) & k_{HL} & k_{HS} \\ 0 & 0 & k_{MB} & -(k_{HL} + k_{HLS}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & k_{HLS} & k_{HS} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where the central term of A_N defines exchanges with inorganic N by a function $(x_{C, MB}, x_{N, MB})$ of C and N contents of microbial biomass.

Both matrix share the rates of enzymatic digestion of labile (k_{VL}) and stable (k_{VS}) plant materials optimal as well as the microbial mortality rate (k_{MB}). These parameters were found linked with another factor determines the organic matters decomposition which is η_{NC} , represent the C: N ratio of the input necromass NC from each plant organ:

$$8. k_{VL} = \text{MAX} (0.65 - 0.0019 \eta_{NC}, 0.1)$$

$$9. k_{VS} = \text{MAX} (0.0037 - 0.000026 \eta_{NC}, 0.00005)$$

$$10. k_{MB} = \text{MIN} (0.42 + 0.0012 \eta_{NC}, 0.8)$$

For MOMOS-C carbon the model vector x is:

$$11. x = \begin{pmatrix} x_{C VL} \\ x_{C VS} \\ x_{C MB} \\ x_{C HL} \\ x_{C HS} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where x_{VL} , x_{VS} , x_{MB} , x_{HL} and x_{HS} represent the C content of the VL, VS, MB, HL and HS compartments, respectively.

For MOMOS-N carbon the model vector x is:

$$12. x = \begin{pmatrix} x_{N VL} \\ x_{N VS} \\ x_{N MB} \\ x_{N HL} \\ x_{N HS} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where $x_{N VL}$, $x_{N VS}$, $x_{N MB}$, $x_{N HL}$ and $x_{N HS}$ represent the N content of the VL, VS, MB, HL and HS compartments, respectively.

For each incubation period, the derivative of total C is:

$$13. \dot{C} = \sum_{i=1}^5 x_{i,C} = -f(\Theta) f(T) x_{C, MB} q_{CO_2}$$

And For each incubation period, the derivative of the total organic N is the negative of the derivative of total inorganic N and is expressed by:

$$14. \dot{N} = \sum_{i=1}^5 x_{i,N} = -f(x_{C, MB}, x_{N, MB}) = -\left(x_{N, MB} - \frac{x_{C, MB}}{\eta_{MB}^{lim}} \right)$$

($x_{C, MB}, x_{N, MB}$) is defined in terms of η_{MB}^{lim} the target value for the C:N ratio of the MB (η_{MB}). Where positive values of the function correspond to N mineralization of microbial N and negative values correspond to microbial immobilization of inorganic N.

III.1.1. Modelling production of plants

The module assumes that plant growth is also controlled by $f(T)f(\theta)$, the climate correction factor used for microbial functioning (Eq. 1), and by aerial biomass C based on the foliar area of each plant species. In order to consider the link between C and N in the photosynthesis process, we have connected the aerial N stocks to the daily C production $\frac{dDCP^j}{dt}$, so the update equation is:

$$15. \frac{dDCP^j}{dt} = f(T)f(\theta) \tau y_{CA}^j \sqrt{y_{NA}^j} (1 - y_{CA}^j / \max y^j).$$

Another new approach was taken in the side of the nitrogen storage, assuming a new parameters regulating the daily production of nitrogen $\frac{dDNP^j}{dt}$ which are the rate of net nitrogen production τ_{NPN}^j and the maximum N biomasses $N \max y^j$, and they were directly related to the C cycle trough the maximum C biomasses and aerial C stocks:

$$16. \frac{dDNP^j}{dt} = f(T)f(\theta) \tau y_{CA}^j (1 - y_{CA}^j / \max y^j) (\tau_{NPN}^j y_{NA}^j) (1 - y_{NA}^j) / N \max y^j$$

The N and C stock of seed grain was considered the first resource of plant growth until the production of their first leaves, organs responsible for the photosynthesis process and the roots, the mean organs responsible for the nutriment uptake from the soil. All C and N productions was partly allocated to roots (R) using allocation rates τ_{AR}^j for the C transfers and τ_{NRS}^j for N allocations. Another part was transferred with the time functions f_1^j to the grains production during their growth, using the same allocation rates τ_{AG}^j for both elements, which was different from the other version of MOMOS where the transfer of N to the seeds was regulated by the allocation rate τ_{NAG}^j the change was based on an assumption that says the new C/N grain ratio is the same ratio existed in the initial grains for each plant j .

During natural mortality and during harvest a part of carbon and nitrogen produced was transferred to the litter by the daily mortality rate τ_{Am}^j and cutting rate τ_H^j

with the time functions f_1^j and f_2^j respectively. The litter was considered to be incorporated into the 0–30 cm by soil macrofauna at a constant daily rate of incorporation τ_{incorp} . In the case of legume, the only resource of carbon for the nodules was considered coming from the photosynthesis process. So during a time function f_3^j a part of DCP was transferred to the nodules with allocation rates τ_{nod}^j .

The aerial C N stocks, for each plant, were then integrated from:

$$17. \frac{dy_{CA}^j}{dt} = C semis^j fsa^j \frac{dDCP^j}{dt} (1 - \tau_{AR}^j - f_1^j(t, \tau_{AG}^j) - f_3^j(t, \tau_{nod}^j)) - y_{CA}^j (f_1^j(t, \tau_{Am}^j) + f_2^j(t, \tau_H^j))$$

$$18. \frac{dy_{NA}^j}{dt} = N semis^j fsa^j + \frac{dDNP^j}{dt} + dy_{NR}^j \tau_{NRS}^j - y_{NA}^j (f_1^j((t + \tau_{Am}^j) + (t + \tau_{AG}^j)) + f_2^j(t, \tau_H^j))$$

The grain C stoks for each plant were then integrated from:

$$19. \frac{dy_{CG(j)}^j}{dt} = f_1^j(t, \tau_{AG}^j) \frac{dDCP^j}{dt} - f_2^j(t) y_{CH}^j$$

Where y_{CH}^j were C exported by grain production of each plant at harvest time.

The grain N stoks for each plant were then integrated from:

$$20. \frac{dy_{NG(j)}^j}{dt} = (f_1^j(t, \tau_{AG}^j) \frac{dDCP^j}{dt}) N semis^j C semis^j - f_2^j(t) y_{NH}^j$$

The litter biomasses C from each plant were integrated from:

$$21. y_{CL}^j = y_{CA}^j (f_1^j(t + \tau_{Am}^j) + f_1^j(t + \tau_H^j)) - y_{CL}^j \tau_{incorp}$$

The litter y_{NL}^j of each plant j was modeled as:

$$22. y_{NL}^j = y_{NA}^j (f_1^j(t + \tau_{Am}^j) + f_1^j(t + \tau_H^j)) - y_{NL}^j \tau_{incorp}$$

For the case of the roots C stocks; it was related in the first place by the rest of the carbon excited in the grain $C semis^j$ and the daily C net production, all outputs are the root respiration τ_{Rr}^j and root mortality τ_{Rm}^j :

$$23. \frac{dy_{CR}^j}{dt} = C semis^j (1 - fsa^j) \tau_{AR}^j \frac{dDCP^j}{dt} - y_{CR}^j (\tau_{Rm}^j + \tau_{Rr}^j)$$

In the other hand, for the roots N stocks, is driven by the N stock of seed grain as initial value regulated by fsa^j , then by the daily inputs of the nitrogen absorbed by the roots with the allocation rate τ_{NRA}^j during the time fuction f_4^j , Beside the N fixed by the nodules

which transfer at the rate τ_{NRR}^j , and by the outputs of the root mortality at the rate τ_{Rm}^j and the N transfer to shoots at the rate τ_{NRS}^j :

$$24. \frac{dy_{NR}^j}{dt} = N_{semis}^j (1 - fsa^j) + f_4^j(t, \tau_{NRA}^j) y_{CR}^j + \tau_{NRR}^j y_{N\ nod}^j y_{NR}^j (\tau_{NRS}^j + \tau_{Rm}^j)$$

The nitrogen contents in the nodules $y_{C\ nod}^j$ of a given plant j was driven by:

$$25. \frac{dy_{C\ nod}^j}{dt} = f_3^j(t, \tau_{nod}^j) \frac{dDCP^j}{dt} - y_{C\ nod}^j (f_1^j(t, \tau_{rnod}^j) + t, \tau_{mnod}^j)$$

$f_3^j(t, \tau_{nod}^j)$ regulates the allocation of plant C production to the nodules, the other terms regulate the losses of the legume nodular C stock by mortality $f_1^j(t, \tau_{rnod}^j)$ and respiration function $f_1^j(t, \tau_{mnod}^j)$.

The N stock in the legume symbiotic nodules was driven by:

$$26. \frac{dy_{N\ nod}^j}{dt} = \tau_{NNF}^j y_{C\ nod}^j f_3^j(t) - y_{N\ nod}^j (\tau_{mnod}^j + \tau_{NRR}^j)$$

Where the first term on the right-hand-side expresses the N inputs from symbiotic fixation τ_{NNF}^j related to the nodular C stock with the function time f_3^j and the second term express the N loss from the nodule to roots τ_{NRR}^j and litter τ_{mnod}^j .

The daily change in the inorganic N compartment was modeled to be related to the sum of MB mineralization or immobilization and to possible addition of inorganic N fertilizer with the rate aiN while his output are root absorptions for each plant j and the global loss flow of inorganic N in environment with the rates τ_{Nloss} :

$$27. \frac{d\ inorg\ N}{dt} = f(X_C, MB, X_N, MB) + f_5^j(t, aiN) - \sum_j f_4^j(t, \tau_{NRA}^j) y_{CR}^j - \tau_{Nloss} \ inorg\ N$$

III.2. Data collection

The data used in this study is collected from the field experiments were carried out over two cropping seasons (2012 and 2013). At the Setif region (at 300 Km North-east of Algiers), a region with a cereal vocation characterized by cold winters and a very hot, long and dry summer. The multilocal field experiments were conducted at The two experimental sites; KasrAbtal (S1) situated in North (35°58, N and 5°14, 9' E) and Baida Bordj (S2), which located in the South of Setif area (35°53, N and 5°37, 01' E), The mean annual temperature across the sites ranged between 14 and 15°C, and the mean annual rainfall ranged between 450 and 500 mm. The choice of this site is justified by the results

of Latati *et al.*, (2016 and 2017) who reported a high efficiency use of rhizobial symbiosis and the presence of P-deficient and calcareous soils. These two experimental sites were chosen at the basis of their soil P availability (low P level of 5.5 mg P kg⁻¹ in S1 and adequate P level of 21.8 mg P kg⁻¹ in S2, Table 1) as to study whether intercropping “maize-common” may alleviate the low P availability in soil. All the physicochemical characteristics of the soil as well as the experimental device were previously reported by Latati *et al.*, (2016) presented in table:

Table 1: Physical and chemical soil properties of the experimental sites S1(p-deficient) and S2(p-sufficient). Values represent the mean of 4 replicates ± SE (standard errors).

Sites	Clay (%)	Loam (%)	Sand (%)	pH	CaCO ₃ (%)	N (g kg ⁻¹)	OM (%)	Total-P (mg kg ⁻¹)	Olsen-P (mg kg ⁻¹)
S1	41.6 ± 0.7 ^a	31.3 ± 0.09 ^b	26.8 ± 0.2 ^a	8.1 ± 0.01 ^a	24.6 ± 0.4 ^a	0.9 ± 0.03 ^b	1 ± 0.08 ^a	95.7 ± 2.9 ^b	5.5 ± 0.3 ^b
S2	40.5 ± 0.3 ^a	33.2 ± 0.2 ^a	26.3 ± 0.2 ^a	7.9 ± 0.07 ^a	23.9 ± 0.1 ^a	2.3 ± 0.12 ^a	1.2 ± 0.05 ^a	257.3 ± 8.1 ^a	21.8 ± 0.6 ^a
<i>p</i> -Value	0.2	<0.001	0.14	0.17	0.19	<0.001	0.25	<0.001	<0.001

The data used for the calibration and validation were collected at four stages of growth: 20 days after sowing (DAS), early flowering (50 DAS), full flowering (75–80 DAS) and at harvest stage (112 DAS). The data included physicochemical characterization of the initial soil .the carbon and nitrogen stock existing in the different parts of plants: grains, shoots, roots, nodules for legumes and in the microbial biomass also the total N and C of the soil.

Figure 3: Localisation of the experimental sites (<https://fr.wikipedia.org/>).

III.3. Calculation tools

III.3.1. VENSIM

Vensim is a visual modelling tool that allows you to conceptualize, document, simulate, analyze, and optimize models of dynamic systems. Vensim provides a simple and flexible way of building simulation models from causal loop or stock and flow diagrams.

By connecting words with arrows, relationships among system variables are entered and recorded as causal connections. This information is used by the Equation Editor form a complete simulation model. The software helps to explore the behavior of the model also to analyze models throughout the building process, looking at the causes and uses of a variable, and also at the loops involving the variable.

VENSIM professional for windows version 5.10d was used for the moisture calculations using the SAHEL .In addition, the update MOMOS model was used for the daily prediction of the C and N cycle's evolution during the vegetative cycle for the Maize /common bean intercropping.

III.4. MOMOS Calibration process

Validation of a model rests in part on comparing model behavior to time series data collected in the "real world." When a model is structurally complete and simulates properly, calibration of the model can proceed. Calibration involves finding the values of model Constants that make the model generate behavior curves that best fit the real world data. The process will attempt to match model variables to data for those variables. A calibration payoff requires that a data file be specified.

In order to use optimization, we need to define what is good and what is bad — called the payoff. The payoff is a measure, reported at the end of the calibration, stating numerically how well the simulation. In the case of calibration process: The payoff for a model can be defined in terms of a comparison of model variables with actual data. These types of payoffs are known as calibration payoffs.

Weight is the amount of weight we want to give to the error between the variable and what you are comparing it to, act to balance the numerical sizes of the different variables, these weights were chosen to be approximately equal to the one over the standard deviation of each variables. It will be positive for calibration payoffs.

III.4.1. Calibration Payoffs Computation

The way in which the payoff is computed depends on the type of payoff. In the case of our study we used calibration payoffs without Kalman Filtering, so at each TIME STEP the data for variables to be compared is checked to see if a value is available. If it is available, the difference between the data and the model variable is multiplied by the weight specified and this product is then squared. This number, which is always positive, is then subtracted from the payoff so that the payoff is always negative. Maximizing the payoff means getting it to be as close to zero as possible.

The weight on a variable should be set to be proportional to the reciprocal of the standard deviation of the prediction error for that variable. If this is done, the expected value of the payoff will be equal to (the negative of) the number of data points. In this manner the 95% confidence interval can be determined by finding a change of 4 in the payoff.

III.4.2. Optimization

To optimize is, quite simply, to achieve the best. Optimization requires that you define a payoff function that summarizes how good a simulation with a single number. Vensim will perform multiple simulations on the model to find the optimum Constant values in order to fit the output with the real world data. After defining the payoff, we select which Constants to vary in order to maximize the payoff. Once we have chosen these Constants with their maximum and minimum bounds (optional), the optimizer will automatically vary them and look for the best fit between the simulation output and your real world data and try to find the values for those parameters that make the payoff as big as possible.

III.4.3. Computing Confidence Bounds

The Constant values found during optimization have some uncertainty around them and we can get a better handle on that uncertainty by testing the sensitivity of the payoff around the optimum which allows us to find out how sensitive the payoff is to changes in parameter values. For this particular problem we have chosen weights so that the default payoff value sensitivity will give 95% confidence bounds. The Payoff Value used is 4

IV. Results

IV.1. Sahel estimation

Figure 6 shows the average air temperature for both sites during the cropping period. Overall, the daily mean temperature for both sites was reasonably stable during the two experimental years. It was estimated at 24.77 °C for the 2012 season which ranged between 12.47°C and 31.46°C. And during the second cropping season, the daily mean temperature was estimated at 22.594°C varied between 15.238°C and 33.282°C for both sites.

The measured values of water content in the upper (5–10 cm) and lower layers of soil (15–30 mm) agreed mostly with the simulations of the SAHEL model. The 5–10 cm soil layer was estimated to hold between 0.1064–0.2873 mm water mm⁻¹ in S1 and between 0.1117–0.3725 mm water mm⁻¹ in S2. While, the deeper layer have values ranging between 0.07788–0.2709 mm water mm⁻¹ for the first experimental site, and the second one was estimated to hold between 0.00907–0.3478 mm water mm⁻¹.

Figure 4: Daily humidity modelled and measured in the surface layer of the soil wcl2 (a) that deeper wcl3 (b) under S1 conditions during the crop cycle conditions.

Figure 5: Daily humidity modelled and measured in the surface layer of the soil wcl2 (a) that deeper wcl3 (b) under S2 conditions during the crop cycle conditions.

Figure 6: The average air temperature for both sites during the cropping time.

Table 2: The R^2 between modelled and measured values and their respective p values at $p < 0.05$ for Maize and common bean under both intercropping and sole cropping system during the two growing seasons

			BM		N BM		Respiration		Y _{CA}		Y _{Cnod}		Y _{Nnod}		Y _{NA}	
			Common		Common		Common		Common		Common		Common		Common	
			bean	Maize	bean	Maize	bean	Maize	bean	Maize	bean	Maize	bean	Maize	bean	Maize
S1	Intercrop	R ²	0,99	0,78	0,75	0,7	0,64	0,91	0,38	0,95	0,72	–	0,98	–	0,71	0,96
		p-Value	≤0.001	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,02	≤0.001	0,1	≤0.001	≤0.001	–	≤0.001	–	0,01	≤0.001
	Sole crop	R ²	0,86	0,48	0,97	0,07	0,95	0,99	0,99	0,98	0,27	–	0,84	–	0,98	0,99
		p-Value	≤0.001	0,04	≤0.001	0,52	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	0,2	–	0,01	–	≤0.001	≤0.001
S2	Intercrop	R ²	0,98	0,96	0,93	0,91	0,54	0,98	0,89	0,58	0,95	–	0,98	–	0,86	0,97
		p-Value	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	0,03	≤0.001	≤0.001	0,03	≤0.001	–	≤0.001	–	0,01	≤0.001
	Sole crop	R ²	0,89	0,99	0,95	0,96	0,94	0,99	0,56	0,76	0,64	–	0,58	–	0,87	0,95
		p-Value	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	≤0.001	0,03	0,01	0,03	–	0,08	–	≤0.001	≤0.001

IV.2. The calibration results

Table 3,4,5,6 represente the calibration and the optimization results for the MOMOS paramerts for both cropping system applied on the maize and the common bean (sole cropping and the intercropping) and for both experimental sites and growing seasons. It included the eco- physiological parameters involved in the carbon exchanges and also those parameters for the Nitrogen exchanges. So, it shows the fitted values for each growth parameter involved in plant production and C transfer to the plants. It also includes (i) the measured maximum Biomass of each plant and the max of N existed in the biomasses , (ii) time function parameters which regulate periods of grain, litter and nodule formation during cropping, (iii) initial values of MOMOS compartments (iv) values of C0 MB, and values of N0 MB (MB at steady state) τ_{incorp} (rate of incorporation of litter to soil by macrofauna,). All other values previously found for MOMOS parameters were retained for this study.

Table 3: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil N compartments of the cropping systems in S1. Only the Values of N_{maxy}^j are measured on the site; the other values are optimised for the best prediction of the whole data set.

Function	Parameter			Cropping system					
				2012			2013		
	Symbol	Description	Units	Maize	Common bean	interc	Maize	Common bean	interc
Growth parameters	τ_{NRA}	Inorganic N absorption rate	$g^{-1}root\ C\ d^{-1}$	0.0185		0.0863525	0.0740481		0.1
$j \in [Maize]$	N_{maxy}	Maximal N production	d^{-1}	59,572212		66,228668	53,671781		35,453833
	τ_{NRS}	N transfer rate to shoots	d^{-1}	0.564497		0.691083	0.355113		0.403944
	τ_{NPN}	N net production	d^{-1}	1.235e-005		0.0001	0.0008546		0.0001624
Growth parameters	τ_{NRA}	Inorganic N absorption rate	$g^{-1}root\ C\ d^{-1}$		0.0677254	0.0004227		0.0739965	0.0045841
$j \in [Common\ bean]$	N_{maxy}	Maximal N production	d^{-1}		48,761185	18,808593		43,025570	13,323133
	τ_{NRS}	N transfer rate to shoots	d^{-1}		0.537191	0.553035		0.990001	0.53868
	τ_{NPN}	N net production	d^{-1}		8.054e-006	1.06e-006		8.06e-006	0.000262
	τ_{NNF}	Rate of symbiotic fixation	$g^{-1}N\ d^{-1}$		0.0004752	0.0008261		0.0010605	0.0016268
	τ_{NNR}	N transfer rate from nodules to root	d^{-1}		0.934026	0.934026		0.929653	1
	N_{MB}^0	MB-N at steady state	$g.N.m^{-2}$	0,0705		0,086	0,0145		0,0956
					2,17	1,299		4,845	5,274
NBM	N HL	N of Labile humus		48,38		6,805	17,1		105,28
$j \in [Maize]$	N HS	N of Stable humus	$g.N.m^{-2}$	4,629		3,082	1,759		11,43
$j \in [Common\ bean]$			$g.N.m^{-2}$		75,82	21,75		0,0351	1,427
					45,42	286,274		1654	96,39
C:N ratios $j \in [Maize]$	η_{MB}	MB C:N threshold ratio for		14.5569		12.5184	24.2031		11.6633
$j \in [Common\ bean]$		mineralization/immobilization	–		12.3851	23.098		21.3738	11.1829

Table 4: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil N compartments of the cropping systems in S2. only the values of N_{max}^j measured on the site; the other values are optimised for the best prediction of the whole data set. Eq. are equation numbers in the text

Function	Parameter			Cropping system					
				2012			2013		
				Symbol	Description	Units	Maize	Common bean	interc
Growth parameters	τ_{NRA}	Inorganic N absorption rate	$g^{-1}root\ C\ d^{-1}$	0,0519776		0.0708273	0,012077		0.0505991
j∈[Maize]	N_{max}^j	Maximal N production	d^{-1}	99,16639		73,473986	75,692763		59,147276
	τ_{NRS}	Allocation rate to shoots	d^{-1}	0.988871		0.506017	0,140332		0.53562
	τ_{NPN}	N net production	d^{-1}	0,0011246		0.0007275	0.025935		0.00014
Growth parameters	τ_{NRA}	Inorganic N absorption rate	$g^{-1}root\ C\ d^{-1}$		0.00118	0.0014304		0.0280959	0.0013868
j∈[Common bean]	N_{max}^j	Maximal N production	d^{-1}		49,404378	42,068523		43,945444	36,488246
	τ_{NRS}	Allocation rate to shoots	d^{-1}		0.979823	0.640205		0.47297	0.525554
	τ_{NPN}	N net production	d^{-1}		1.06e-006	1,00E-05		1,00E-05	1.096e-006
	τ_{NNF}	Rate of symbiotic fixation	$g^{-1}N\ d^{-1}$		0.0111623	0.0026919		0.001135	0.0004790
	τ_{NNR}	N transfer rate from nodules to root	d^{-1}		1	0.934026		0.945698	0.935963
	N_{MB}^0	MB-N at steady state	$g.N.m^{-2}$	0,064		4,873	0,0738		4,576
					3,832	0,126		0,0894	0,6499
NBM	N HL	N of Labile humus	$g.N.m^{-2}$	106,43		14,03	54,98		24,16
j∈[Maize]	N HS	N of Stable humus	$g.N.m^{-2}$	18,66		28,35	77,05		5,986
j∈[Common bean]					0,1604	0,3932		0,2235	0,0689
					13213	496,77		49,83	217,87
C:N ratios j∈[Maize]	η_{MB}	MB C:N threshold ratio for	–	15,6308		22.2492	22,0261		12.2835
j∈[Common bean]		mineralization/immobilization			15.9635	15.8151		11.2426	15.0422

Table 5: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil C compartments of the cropping systems in S1

Function	Parameter			Cropping system					
				2012			2013		
				Symbol	Description	Units	Maize	Common bean	interc
Growth parameters	τ	Relative growth rate	day ⁻¹	0.408294		0.594403	0.57384		0.522375
j∈[Maize]	τ_{AR}	Allocation rate to roots	–	0.459851		0.540346	0.683576		0.534751
	τ_{AG}	Transfer rate to grain	–	0.315711		0.49663	0.589347		0.474562
	maxy	Maximal production	g.C.m ⁻²	1793,9821		1586,5817	1311,5349		1195,1697
Mortality	τ_{Rm}	Root mortality rate	d ⁻¹	0.1		0.1	0.0670016		0.1
	τ_{Am}	Aerial mortality rate	d ⁻¹	0.174515		1.954e-006	0.0001		0.0001
Respiration	τ_{Rr}	Root resp. rate, cereal	d ⁻¹	0.0999953		0.1	0.1		0.099881
Growth parameters	τ	Relative growth rate	d ⁻¹		0.662117	0.542415		0.626283	0.63315
j∈[Common bean]	τ_{AR}	Allocation rate to roots	–		0.255014	0.194375		0.302914	0.241549
	τ_{AG}	Transfer rate to grain	–		0.999999	0.460602		0.701774	0.542187
	τ_{nod}	Allocation rate to Nodule	–		0.00073	0.0006615		0.00073	0.001310
	maxy	Maximal production.	g.C.m ⁻²		664,85360	216,80494		493,35119	184,50916
Mortality	τ_{Rm}	Root mortality rate	d ⁻¹		8.269e-005	0,1		0,1	0.1
	τ_{Am}	Aerial mortality rate	d ⁻¹		0.0380716	0.141842		0.0001	0.136566
	τ_{mmod}	Nodule mortality rate	d ⁻¹		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.1
Respiration	τ_{Rr}	Root resp rate, legume	d ⁻¹		0.0763211	0,1		0,1	0,1
Litter incorporation	τ_{incorp}	Litter to soil	d ⁻¹						
j∈[Maize]		incorporation rate		0.0025669		0.0025669	0.0003		1
j∈[Common bean]					0.0721242	0.776859		1	0.9997
Time function f1(t)	Ot ^j	Opt time grain growth	day.	0.192897		0.192897	0.192897		0.192897
j∈[Maize]	Dt ⁱ	Dev. time grain growth	d	77.4571		100.205	91.9069		98.2022
j∈[Common bean]					0.192897	0.171297		0.192897	0.192897
					71.7393	83.6754		88.7221	83.4665
Time function f3(t)	Ot ^{i_{nod}}	Opt time nodule growth	d		5	21.5778		8.21532	25.2556
nodules	Dt ^{i_{nod}}	Dev time nodule growth	d		0.0190014	0.0241174		0.0187525	0.0363329
MB j∈[Maize]	C _{MB} ⁰	MB-C at steady state	g.C.m ⁻²	1,018		1,079	0,4199		38,18
j∈[Common bean]					60	30,01		26,52	60
x initial values	HL	Labile humus	g.C.m ⁻²	590,93		495,05	453,85		4066
humus j∈[Maize]	HS	Stable humus	g.C.m ⁻²	92,58		154,11	40,45		438,76
j∈[Common bean]					261,81	547,71		14,69	73,99
					2725	538,36		287,12	159,62
x initial values	VS1	of cereal roots	g.C.m ⁻²	64.2224		0	5		150
plant debris	VS2	of legume roots	g.C.m ⁻²	50		50	50		50
j∈[Maize]	VS3	of cereal litter	g.C.m ⁻²	51.9987		0	0		5
	VS4	of legume litter	g.C.m ⁻²	50		50	50		50
					50	50		50	50
					180.505	74.3095		250	249.932
j∈[Common bean]					50	50		50	50
					250	23.426		234.734	123.774

Table 6: Eco-physiological parameters and initial values of soil C compartments of the cropping systems in S2

Function	Parameter			Cropping system					
				2012			2013		
				Symbol	Description	Units	Maize	Common bean	interc
Growth parameters	τ	Relative growth rate	day ⁻¹	0.408294		0.292701	0.578086		0.195759
j∈[Maize]	τ_{AR}	Allocation rate to roots	–	0.459851		0.198952	0.737044		0.309182
	τ_{AG}	Transfer rate to grain	–	0.315711		0.911046	0.720066		0.730945
	maxy	Maximal production	g.C.m ⁻²	2396,4574		2146,5199	1805,4444		1739,6456
Mortality	τ_{Rm}	Root mortality rate	d ⁻¹	0,042518		0.0197883	0.0999364		0.0128885
	τ_{Am}	Aerial mortality rate	d ⁻¹	0,0212283		0.103249	0.0999364		0.044099
Respiration	τ_{Rr}	Root resp. rate, cereal	d ⁻¹	0,1		0.0442501	5.364e-006		0.0487308
Growth parameters	τ	Relative growth rate	d ⁻¹		0.285687	0.281214		0.380171	0.400228
j∈[Common bean]	τ_{AR}	Allocation rate to roots	–		0.322161	0.315416		0.405036	0.438459
	τ_{AG}	Transfer rate to grain	–		0.762608	0.551716		0.89801	0.999801
	τ_{nod}	Allocation rate to Nodule	–		0.0195036	0.0013104		0.0017432	0.0013104
	maxy	Maximal production.	g.C.m ⁻²		493,881102	487,74411		429,92734	439,56623
Mortality	τ_{Rm}	Root mortality rate	d ⁻¹		0.1	0.1		0.0697939	0.1
	τ_{Am}	Aerial mortality rate	d ⁻¹		0.013827	0.1		0.373444	2.015e-005
	τ_{mmod}	Nodule mortality rate	d ⁻¹		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.1
Respiration	τ_{Rr}	Root resp rate, legume	d ⁻¹		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.0993158
Litter incorporation	τ_{incorp}	Litter to soil incorporation rate	d ⁻¹						
j∈[Maize]				0,536596		0.0006539	0.005		1,00E-05
j∈[Common bean]					0.999866	1		1.059e-006	1.002e-006
Time function f1(t)	Ot ^j	Opt time grain growth	day.	0,192897		0.192897	0.192897		0.171297
j∈[Maize]	Dt ⁱ	Dev. time grain growth	d	97,7392		86.5532	101.558		79.6299
j∈[Common bean]					0.192897	0.1294989.		0.192897	0.129494
					91.3891	75.81		84.408	107.503
Time function f3(t)	Ot ^{i_{nod}}	Opt time nodule growth	d		1.66909	29.8152		5	30
nodules	Dt ^{i_{nod}}	Dev time nodule growth	d		0.0368646	0.0288928		0.028075	0.0359853
MB j∈[Maize]	C _{MB} ⁰	MB-C at steady state	g.C.m ⁻²	1		60	1		60
j∈[Common bean]					60	1,996		1,001	8,362
x initial values	HL	Labile humus	g.C.m ⁻²	3253		394,38	569,18		27,45
humus j∈[Maize]	HS	Stable humus	g.C.m ⁻²	1120		602,26	3852		299,19
j∈[Common bean]					0,0405	124,54		50,01	21,13
					904,74	479,33		32,64	290,42
x initial values	VS1	of cereal roots	g.C.m ⁻²	160.3		118.232	210.947		10
plant debris	VS2	of legume roots	g.C.m ⁻²	50		50	50		50
j∈[Maize]	VS3	of cereal litter	g.C.m ⁻²	246.059		123.282	5.0735		10
j∈[Common bean]	VS4	of legume litter	g.C.m ⁻²	50		50	50		50
					50	50		50	50
					250	250		244.444	250
					50	50		50	50
					249.378	250		246.581	250

IV.3. Biomass production and transfer of C and N in the various organs of the plant

F tests showed that the measured data and modelled values were all within the 95 % confidence intervals, exception for N stocks for the intercropped common bean shoots and nodular C stocks of the sole crop for S1 during the first growing, they were not significant at $p < 0, 1$ and $p < 0, 2$ respectively. Moreover, the predicted values were all positively correlated with the measured values. However, the transfer of C and N in the shoot substantially varied in response to cropping treatments, the experimental sites, and the growing seasons. After sowing and during the first days of plant growth, both species show slow storage of CN, and then it starts to accelerate gradually in conjunction with the appearance of the roots and leaves. During flowering, the CN allocations rates to the shoots were at their highest levels. Especially for the sole crop maize where the simulation shows that the CN transfer was higher than the intercropping system under S1 conditions and this increase was noticed more during the 2012 season than 2013. In the case of S2, the prediction shows that the C transfer of the intercropped Maize increased better than when it cultivated alone during the first season, but in the second year, it was completely the opposite. For the N shoots, we can observe that a large amount of N was allocated to the shoots of the sole maize crop, but in the 2013 season, the transfers were almost equal. Nevertheless, the CN transfer for the intercropped common bean was lower than the sole cropping for both growing season and experimental sites. The C stock for the shoots and roots will transfer to the grains during their formation, which gives a temporary decrease of C in other aerial parts, especially for Maize.

The measured and simulated values of CN stored in nodules of the common bean are shown in the Fig. 9. The CN transfer in the common bean plants was predicted as having a quasi-linear increase after sowing reaching the peak (between 51 and 80 DAS) which was considerably lower in the mixed crop compared to sole crop under S1 and S2 conditions for both seasons, especially for the intercropping common bean in S1 during the first season when N-Nod was estimated at 0.1577 g Nm^{-2} . C-Nod was estimated at 0.0102 g Cm^{-2} after 70DAS. Finally, the simulation decreases quasi-linearly until it ceased at harvest time.

Figure 7: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled aerial C stocks in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean. And modelled aerial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.

Figure 8: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled aerial C stocks in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b)common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled aerial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.

Figure 10 shows the cumulated N fixation for the common bean during the cropping period. The model predicts that the intercropping have a low amount of N rested in the soil after harvest compared to the single cropping. The highest predicted values were estimated during 2012 at 0.1964 g Nm^{-2} and 0.276 g Nm^{-2} for the common bean of the sole crops plots in S1 and S2 respectively.

IV.4. Transfer of C and N to microbial biomass

Figure 11 and 12 shows the measured and simulated values of the microbial CN stock in S1 and S2, respectively. The measured values corresponded with the model predictions significantly (F-test) with a strong correlation exception for N microbial outputs in S1; they were not inside the confidence intervals of the measured values. Fig.11a, c, e, g and fig.a, e shows an increase in the day after sowing, and this could be related to the irrigation applied. Then it starts to decrease during the following days because of the low inputs of OM. For the rest of the figures, the modelled one shows a decrease at sowing due to soil tillage which causes perturbation of microbial communities, after that, the modelled start to increase during the flowering period simultaneously with the CN stocks in the shoots, and continued to grow during the formation of the grains which was probably due to the additional debris inputs. The simulation shows that CN BM of the mixed crop (both Maize and common bean) in the growing season 2013 increased better than the sole crops, and clearly noticed in S1 compared to S2 by recording high values of CN storage. The same results were noted during 2012 season in S1, but it was quite the opposite for S2 during the same season where CN BM of the mixed crops was lower than the sole crops. In the other hand, this increase was very clear in the common bean rhizosphere where we note the highest predicted values estimated at C BM= 62.24 g.C.m^2 , 55.47 g.C.m^2 , N BM= 4.312 g.N.m^2 , 4.89 g.N.m^2 for the intercropping common bean in S1 during both growing seasons

Figure 10: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled nodular C stocks of the pure cropping and the intercropping in a) S1 b) S2. And modelled nodular N stocks of the pure cropping and the intercropping c) S1 d) S2.

Figure 9: The cumulated N fixation for the sole crop and the intercropping in a) S1 b) S2

Figure 11: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled microbial C stocks in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean . And modelled microbial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.

Figure 12: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled microbial C stocks in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean. And modelled microbial N stocks of the pure cropping e) maize f) common bean and the intercropping g) Maize h) common bean.

IV.5. Transfer of C by total soil respiration

Figure 13 and 14 shows predicted values of the total respiration of the soil, they were all within the 95 % confidence intervals of the measured values. Thus, the coefficient of determination R^2 shows a positive correlation between the outputs and the inputs data. Carbon dioxide (CO_2) emission from the soil surface is an indicator of the overall activity of soil micro-organisms and the root-nodule symbiosis. A large amount of CO_2 flux was predicted for the earlier stages of the vegetal cycle which continue to increase following the plant growth and CN storage in the microbial communities, until the finale periods of the flowering stage where the max values were predicted for the Maize and common bean in S1 during 2012 notably higher in pure crops than the mixed crops which we demonstrated. Previously, it has the highest CN transfer rates to the shoots and the highest CN exchange with MB during the same period.

Figure 13: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled daily respiration in S1 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean

Figure 15: The measured with 95% confidence intervals and the modelled daily respiration in S2 of the pure cropping a) maize b) common bean, and the intercropping c) maize d) common bean

V. Discussion

V.1. Robustness of the model and the ecophysiological estimates

Parameters determinations were considered as the most important in our modelling approach. Most of the C and N models published over past decades are based on parameters and did not always link to the environment and underestimate the role of micro-organisms. According to Ibrahim *et al.*, (2016) and Pansu *et al.*, (2018), they are often over-parameterized, they can give multiple solutions for flow calculations between state variables. MOMOS studies are based on reducing the complexity of the model and validating the equation system by suggesting the minimum number of well-defined parameters (Ockham's razor, *lex parsimoniae*). With the large variations due to environmental conditions and with the various limitations existing in this field, determining the ecophysiological parameters are difficult to implement, and the results are subjective. For that matter, the modelling method enables the simultaneous calculation of exchange parameters with great importance in plant physiology, by optimization against state variables of C and N stocks. The precision of their estimation allowed us to understand better the behaviour of the CN flows for each compartment at a daily time step, especially for the intercropping cereal-legumes system, which presents very complex interactions series. However, the different simulation results for all the variables studied showed positive correlations with the data measured in the field, and most of them showed a solid fit based on the F test by presenting a risk lower than 5%. This evidence proves the solidity of the model for the estimation of these ecophysiological parameters.

V.2. Plant growth and grain yield

The calculated relative growth rate shows high values for the intercropped Maize in S1 compared to their unique culture, while it was not the case for the second experimental site. However, the common bean has values that range from 0.54 day⁻¹ to 0.66 day⁻¹ in S1 and from 0.28 day⁻¹ to 0.4 day⁻¹ in S2. We note that these estimated values were higher than those estimated by Ibrahim *et al.*, (2016), perhaps it's because we are applying on a summer cropping system where the amount of photosynthesis is important. The highest optimization values for the Maize pure crops were observed

during the 2013 season in both sites, and for the common bean pure crops, it was found under P deficiency condition during the first year. These estimations can explain the increase for the predictions of the shoots C stocks in these sites in comparison to their mixed crop. Furthermore, the predictions of y_{CA} have shown a strong fit with the data which confirms the new assumption proposed for daily C production and for that the N flows will take place in the carbon storage in the plant through the photosynthesis process.

Parts of the daily C production will be transferred to the roots with an allocation rate τ_{AR}^j it was estimated at 0.54, 0.43 for the Maize mixed crop in S1 for the first growing season and the intercropped common bean in S2 for the next growing season respectively. It was estimated during the 2013 growth season at 0.46 and 0.3 for the sole crop of the common bean in S1 and the Maize in S2 respectively. The optimization of these parameters has associated with a decrease in C stocks in the shoots compared to their other crop system. This could mean that the C results from photosynthesis process will be used with higher values for the root growth caused by that the decrease for the C storage in the shoots. Furthermore, the higher values return to the mixed Maize under the P deficiency, which could be an outcome from the various interactions with the common bean under this condition for the nutrition uptake. This shows us a clear intercropping advantage in terms of total RDW and more so under deficient (S1) than sufficient (S2) P conditions. Similar results were found for the intercropping of these two species reported by Latati *et al.*, (2013; 2016).

The increase of cereal grain yield by intercropped legume has been reported in the literature. For intercropping system, grain yield of either Maize was increased when intercropped with faba bean (Li *et al.*, 2007; Kaci *et al.*, 2018), Cowpea (Eskandari, 2012; Li *et al.*, 2005). This increase in wheat productivity in intercropping has also been reported by Huňady and Hochman, (2014). They found that grain yield of wheat was higher in intercropping with faba bean than in monocropping. The allocation rates to the grains τ_{AG}^j for the intercropped Maize were higher than the sole crops for S1 during 2012 and S2 during 2013 growing season. For the intercropped common bean, it was lower than the pure crop in S1 and S2 during 2012 and 2013 respectively, indicating that the yield could be increased for the Maize and could be decreased for the common bean

under the mixed crop system. In the other hand, the N grain is also controlled by the same allocation rates based on our update equation. This means that the N transferred to the seeds could enhance the intercropped Maize and decrease for the legume. Which agree with the results previously published by Latati et al., (2016) for the same cropping system.

V.3. Nodular growth and nitrogen uptake

Nodule biomass for intercropped legumes was found decreased compared to monocropped legumes. A limited number of recent studies have addressed the same effect of intercropping on nodule growth for chickpea and common bean (Betencourt et al., 2012; Latati et al., 2013). Kaci et al., (2018) have also reported this decrease for the intercropped faba bean with drum wheat. The calculated rates of nodules allocations τ_{nod}^j for the intercropping common bean in S2 and S1 for both seasons have confirmed these studies, where the values of monoculture were higher than the other cropping system exception for S1 during 2013 where it was the opposite. Still, it was corrected with the optimum time for the growth of the nodules, which was higher in the intercropping system, for that the model prediction show that the C-nod for the intercropping did not increase. The decrease in nodule biomass could be compensated by an increase in nodule number (Latati et al.,2014), which could be due to a change in the population of efficient rhizobial strains involved in root infection and efficient nodulation with higher nitrogenase activity (Depret and Laguerre, 2008).

Several studies reported an increase in the N₂ fixation for intercropped legumes, as a consequence of the competition with the intercropped cereal for nitrate uptake (Li et al., 2009; Naudin et al., 2010; Dahmardeh et al., 2010). Thus, this mechanism will be maximized in the conditions of the low P availability where the legumes can enhance P acquisition by the increasing N₂ fixation (Betencourt et al., 2012; Latati et al.,2014). In the case of our results, the τ_{NNF}^j for both sites during the second was more significant in the mixed common bean but high under the P deficiency indicating important symbiotic reactions. In the other hand, the N fixation rates will be multiplied by the C nodular biomass to give the values of N nodular based on the previous equation 26. As a result, the amount of N storage will be lower for the intercropping compared to the sole crops,

and this corresponds precisely to the model prediction. However, the simulations of N cumulated fixation shows low values in the rhizosphere of the intercropped common bean. Through the mechanisms of nitrogen partitioning, we can assume that N fixed by the common bean was used with large amounts by the cereal during their growth, so this reveals the positive interactions between these species.

The N absorption rate for roots τ_{NRA}^j was found higher in the intercropping Maize compared to the pure cropping and more than the common bean in both cropping systems where the mixed crops have low values. The highest value for the common bean crop was calculated for the monoculture of the second site during the 2013 season, and they were associated with high values of the root production rate. This clears up the increase noted for the prediction of the model. The smallest value return to the common bean mixed crop under P deficiency estimated at 0.0004 d^{-1} which also typified with the lowest τ_{AR}^j inducing less rhizosphere occupation so less Inorganic N mobilization, this leads to a decrease in the N shoots typically what the model predicted. At the same time, their intercropped cereal has a higher value of root production rate so great high rhizosphere occupation, and for that the N shoot observed was high, this increase is the results of the interspecific competition between this species for the N uptake. A part of the N absorbed will be allocated to the shoots at the rate τ_{NRS}^j . In the P deficiency conditions, the high values were estimated to the intercropping Maize and the common bean sole crop during 2012, 2013 respectively compare to their corresponding crop system. And for the second site, the high values return to the sole crop of the first growing season. Moreover, the optimization has clearly revealed the relationship between the estimations for these crops and those of the relative growth where they also have the highest values compared to their corresponding crop system, even of that, the N shoots show an apparent increase. This results support strongly our new assumption proposed for the model and so the C storage in the plant will have a place in the N cycle through the daily N production by connecting the maximum of C production and the aerial C stocks.

V.4. CN transfer between micro-organism – plant and atmosphere

The modelling method should enable to estimate threshold values of microbial C-to-N ratio regulating immobilization or mineralization of inorganic N from

decomposer micro-organisms, and simultaneously to estimate essential parameters of CN exchanges for plant growth. MOMOS is considered to be the first decomposition model based on the functioning of biomass microbial. Ibrahim *et al.*, (2016) and Pansu *et al.*, (2018) have confirmed his ability to highlight some mechanisms that control the sequestration of C and N between compartments of the system soil-plant-atmosphere-microorganism. The only microbial decomposers and rhizobia have been considered for the prediction of our entire data set.

The microbial action on improvement or depletion of the plant growth of this study, according to the results, it was vary depending on the phenological stages, especially during flowering. In this period the CN transfer to different parts of the plants will be at the highest level, and consequently, the amount of CN flows to the soil will also be high through the mortality of the roots, shoots and nodules which provide additional inputs for the C and N source of energy for micro-organisms communities, which stimulates their growth and activity. In their turn of that, they will increase the availability of N inorganic by mineralization which will be uptake by the root with the rate τ_{NRA}^j during the time function f_4 . This inorganic N could be immobilized by MB; it will be regulated by the threshold η_{MB}^{lim} of the MB C: N ratio. In the other hand, there will be exchanges with the atmosphere via CO₂ which could be used for photosynthesis process simulating by that the plant growth and via N₂ flows which could return to the soil by the nodular symbiotic fixation and used finally by the plant.

From this mechanistic modelling, the micro-organisms appear of prime importance to bind the growth of the plants in intercropping. The daily modelling of CN exchanges between the plant and the soil has clearly revealed the central role played by soil micro-organisms in stimulating CN transfers.

The number and diversity of sites where was applied the microbial part of the model regulating the OM transformations in soil appears again valid in alkaline Mediterranean conditions with new local variables for weather, soil and qualities of inputs from plants., which authorize us to retain the equation system of Pansu *et al.*, (2010, 2014).

VI. Conclusion

Overall the finding reported in this research thesis, the highlighted objectives of the introduction section are mostly attained. Most of the proposed equations system that was recently defined for the parameterization and validation of either MOMOS-C (Ibrahim et al., 2016) or MOMOS-N (Pansu et al., 2018) in faba bean-wheat intercropping shows their validity in summer intercropping system (maize-common bean) at the farmer's plot level. MOMOS parameterization was strongly improved through the measurements of the state variables (plant inputs, soil and weather) regulating the C and N transfers in two contrasting farmer's sites in term of pedoclimatic conditions. In this work, in low-P calcareous soil, the extension of the decomposition part of the MOMOS model at the regional scale (Setif agroecosystem) was successfully done for the second time in alkaline Mediterranean conditions just after that performed at the experimental station in Manguio agroecosystem. The new equations that were formulated in this thesis for both N daily production and N grain stocks (Eq. 16 and 20) show significant complementarities to these previously used in the last published versions of the model (Ibrahim et al., 2016; Pansu et al., 2018). Indeed, another equation relative to C and N exchange between plant organs (Eq. 15, 17, 18, 23, 24 and 26) were carefully checked to better optimize transfer parameters for plant production. These improvements were performed with a limited number of parameters to make sure that equations systems are not over parameterized. In the field conditions of our experiment, this thesis gives the first estimation of C and N exchange rate between the ecophysiological parameters of plants, soil, microbial biomass and symbiotes which are difficult to estimate and to implement by other experimental methods. This provides the opportunity to validate the present calibrated model (MOMOS-C and MOMOS-N) at the plot, farm and regional scales particularly for intercropped species within the short crop cycle (i.e. 3 to 4 months). Results show that all C and N daily exchanges between the plant organs and micro-organisms were strongly varied among the phenological stages. The highest variation was clearly observed during the crop period from the beginning to the end of the flowering stage (50 to 81 DAS). For this period, the significant part of transferred C and N stocks has been detected simultaneously in sole cropping system for nodules and shoots of both species, in particular under P-deficiency conditions (S1). The nodules C

and N transfers began to increase again at the end of the flowering stage for both intercropped species, in which the rate of this increase was more pronounced in low P-soil sites (S1). After that, N stocks in micro-organisms decomposers were markedly increased before N release by mineralization processes of dead common bean nodules, and which were stimulated mainly by the high C availability (from nodule mortalities) for microbial activities. The proposed modelling performed in this research thesis successfully illustrates the robustness of this MOMOS calibrated version to assess and analyze more deeply the mechanisms regulating the global C and N exchanges between the plant symbionts, the soil, the living microbes and the atmosphere. According to these finding, we propose this parameterized MOMOS version for the future approximation of C and N transfer in agroecosystem (particularly for intercropped species within short crop cycle) at regional scales.

VII. Refernece

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